

THERMAL EXPANSION OF COMPOSITES WITH CANVAS-TYPE REINFORCEMENT AND POLYMER MATRIX

J. KABELKA

*Institute of Thermomechanics
Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences, Prague*

A mathematical model is described which enables to calculate the effective thermal expansion coefficients (TEC) and thermal stresses in the structure of composites with textile reinforcement. The model assumes that the fabric has a linen weave and considers the linear-elastic behaviour of constituents, the fabric geometry and temperature dependence of thermo-elastic characteristics of components. Influence of cloth parameters as well as properties of matrix and fibers on TEC and thermal stresses was analysed by means of computer HP 9820. The reliability of the mathematical procedure was estimated comparing the theoretical and experimental results.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of predicting the effective thermal expansion coefficients (TEC) for multiphase has been studied by many authors. Here, we can mention for example the works by Shapery [1], Schneider [2], Levin [3], Rosen and Hashin [4], Van Fo Fy [5], etc. While all mentioned works were devoted to the unidirectional or angle-ply laminates, this paper deals with the problem of TEC of textile-reinforced composites that can be understood as a construction of unidirectionally reinforced strands. Because of anisotropic behaviour of these strands the thermal and mechanical properties are closely coupled and TEC of this type of composite material depends not only on the thermo-mechanical characteristics of constituents but also on the state of internal stresses. An extensive analysis of lamination residual thermal stresses was given by Chamis [6], Wang [7] and Daniel [8], who (using a linear laminate theory) showed that these stresses can reach values comparable to the transverse strength of the ply and thus can induce cracking across the plies. The assumption of linear-elastic behaviour tends to overestimate the residual thermal stresses, nevertheless, gives the first insight into the problem and it seems to be reasonable to undertake the first estimation of our problem in this direction.

MODEL FORMULATION

- a) Reinforcing cloth is of the canvas weave with the regular structure. For this reason we shall consider only one element, the dimensions of which as well as the coordinate system are represented in Fig. 1.
- b) The warp- and weft-yarns have a sine-form-welling and their cross sections parallel with xz and yz planes remain constant. The cross section area can be expressed:

$$F_1 = 2 \int_0^{t_1/2} h_1 \cos(\pi x / t_1) dx = 2h_1 t_1 / \pi \quad (1)$$

- c) The fibers are dispersed regularly in the yarns cross sections and the volume fraction of fibers is in both systems of yarns the same. If the numbers of fibers in the weft and warp yarns are n_1 and n_2 respectively, then

$$\xi = n_1 / n_2 = h_1 t_1 / h_2 t_2 \quad (2)$$

The total thickness $h = h_1 + h_2$ of the cloth is usually known as well as the density Q of the cloth. From Eq. (2) then yields

$$h_1 = \xi h t_2 / (t_1 + \xi t_2) ; \quad h_2 = h - h_1 \quad (3)$$

The volume fraction of fibers in the yarns can be expressed

$$k = \pi Q / 2h \gamma_F \quad (4)$$

and the relative content of fibers by weight in the total volume of the element in question is given by

$$k^+ = 1 / (1 + \gamma_M (H \gamma_F / Q - 1) \gamma_F) \quad (5)$$

- d) The computation element is a block consisting of 3 layers: two mutually perpendicular layers of unidirectional composites and one layer of resin. The thicknesses of layers are functions of the coordinates x and y . At every point in the region

$x \in (-t_1/2 ; t_1/2)$, $y \in (-t_2/2 ; t_2/2)$ hold $\sum h_i = H$.

- e) All layers are linearly elastic, the bonds between adjacent layers are perfect. With respect to c) the thermo-elastic characteristics E_{ii} , E_L , ν_{ii} , G_{ii} , α_{ii} , α_L of unidirectional reinforced layers are identical. Matrix is assumed as linearly elastic, isotropic and is characterized by E_M , ν_M , α_M .
- f) Temperature is at every point of the element identical and is changing from the initial value T to the value $T + \Delta T$. In this temperature interval the thermo-elastic characteristics remain constants. At the initial temperature the system is free of stresses.
- g) The cross-sections parallel with xz and yz planes remain plane.
- h) The influence of yarns welling on the thermo-elastic constants in the x and y directions is neglected.

The change ΔT of temperature induces the stresses σ_{xi} and σ_{yi} in the individual layers which are - with respect to g) - independent on the coordinate z . It yields from the assumption e), that the deformation of all layers in a given point (x,y) is identical and in directions x,y it depends on the variable x and y , respectively:

$$\epsilon_{xi} = F(x) ; \quad \epsilon_{yi} = G(y) \quad (i = 1,2,3) \quad (6)$$

From the Hooke's law yields

$$\begin{aligned} F(x) &= \alpha_{xi} \Delta T + \sigma_{xi} / E_{xi} - \nu_{yxi} \sigma_{yi} / E_{xi} \\ G(y) &= \alpha_{yi} \Delta T + \sigma_{yi} / E_{yi} - \nu_{xyi} \sigma_{xi} / E_{yi} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The balance condition on the plane cross-sections can be written:

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^{t_1/2} h_1 \cos(\pi x/t_1) \sigma_{y1} dx + \int_0^{t_2/2} h_2 \cos(\pi y/t_2) \sigma_{y2} dx + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{t_2/2} (H - h_1 \cos(\pi x/t_1) - h_2 \cos(\pi y/t_2)) \sigma_{y3} dx = 0 \\ &\int_0^{t_2/2} h_1 \cos(\pi x/t_1) \sigma_{x1} dy + \int_0^{t_2/2} h_2 \cos(\pi y/t_2) \sigma_{x2} dy + \\ &\quad + \int_0^{t_2/2} (H - h_1 \cos(\pi x/t_1) - h_2 \cos(\pi y/t_2)) \sigma_{x3} dy = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

If σ_{xi} and σ_{yi} are expressed from Eq.(7) and then introduced into Eq.(8), two equations are obtained for two unknown functions $F(x)$ and $G(y)$. The solution leads to the rather complicated expressions and, therefore, we shall describe only some results.

The effective TEC in the principle directions x and y are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_x &= (2/t_1 \Delta T) \int_0^{t_1/2} F(x) dx \\ \alpha_y &= (2/t_2 \Delta T) \int_0^{t_2/2} G(y) dy \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In the real case, when the temperature interval is too large to accept the temperature-independence of the thermo-elastic characteristics of layers, we divide the given temperature range

into smaller intervals and using Duhamel-Neumann law [11] we solve the problem step by step.

The accuracy of calculation then depends on the fineness of the division.

The mentioned calculation procedure was elaborated into a program for HP 9820 calculator, that enables to analyze the influence of individual quantities on the TEC-value. If the functions $F(x)$ and $G(y)$ are known, the stresses σ_{xi} and σ_{yi} working in the individual layers can be determined by means of Eq. (7).

RESULTS OF NUMERICAL CALCULATION

A typical composite system was used for analysing the influence of the individual characteristics on TEC.

Constitution of material:

Reinforcement: Glas fabric with the specific weight

$$Q = 0.36 \text{ kg/m}^2, h = 0.35 \text{ mm}, \xi = 1 \text{ and } t_1 = t_2 = 1.8 \text{ mm.}$$

Thermoelastic constants of glass fibers:

$$E_F = 70 \text{ GPa}; \nu_F = 0.25; \alpha_F = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}; \gamma_F = 2.54 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3.$$

Matrix:

- a) Polyester resin - after the evaluation of published results the temperature dependence of the deformation characteristics was expressed in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{MP}(T) &= 2.15 - 1.05 \arctg((T-50)/20) \quad [\text{GPa}] \\ \nu_{MP}(T) &= 0.445 - 0.035 \arctg((T-35)/10) \quad [1] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

- b) Epoxy resin: in this case there were used formuli:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{ME}(T) &= 2.25 - 1.432 \arctg((T-95)/20) \quad [\text{GPa}] \\ \nu_{ME}(T) &= 0.4 + 0.0637 \arctg((T-60)/20) \quad [1] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Note: in the expressions (10) and (11) T is considered in centigrades.

Graphical representation of expressions (10) and (11) is shown in Fig.2.

The temperature dependence of α_M was used for both resins the same and corresponds to the behaviour of resin CODE 67 [9]

$$\alpha_M(T) = 4.3 + 4.81(T-20)10^{-2} + 1.289(T-20)^2 10^{-4} \quad [10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}] \quad (12)$$

where also T is considered in $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Expression (12) is illustrated in Fig.3. Density γ_M for both resins equals $1.24 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$. In almost all of the cases the thickness H of the computation element was taken $H = h$.

Elastic constants of the weft and warp strands E_{II} , E_{I} and ν_{II} were determined using formuli given by Puck [10]. For TEC α_{II} and α_{I} were accepted formuli given by Schneider [2].

The calculations were performed for the temperature interval (20,70) and (20,130) $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for polyester and epoxy resins respectively. ΔT was taken 5°C . The state of the composite material at

the starting temperature is assumed to be stress-free. This means that the resulting stresses are thermal stresses. In practice there is very important the case of curing the matrix under the elevated temperature. The stress-free state then corresponds to the curing temperature and during cool-down cycle there are developing the residual stresses in the structure of composite material. These residual stresses are of opposite sign in relation with the thermal ones. The most dangerous of them are the stresses acting perpendicularly to the reinforcing fibers.

TEC AND THERMAL STRESSES FOR THE REFERENCE MATERIAL

In Fig.4 there is illustrated the temperature dependence of TEC for the glass/polyester reference material and in Fig.5 the values of induced thermal stresses for the temperature change $20-70^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the points $(x;0)$. Because of symmetry of the element in question, the stress-curves for the y-axis points would be identical. We can observe that the stress σ_x , which plays the most important role in the fracture process, reaches its highest value at the point $(0,0)$. For this reason we will present the stress-diagrams for this point only. It was already done in Fig.6 showing the increase of stresses with the temperature.

INFLUENCE OF WEAVE DENSITY OF FABRIC

The fabrication conditions such as the value of forces in the yarns decide, how close will be the weave of fabric. The weave density can be represented by the change of the thickness h when all other parameters remain constant. In consequence of that the fraction of fibers in the composite is also changing, how it is demonstrated in Fig.7 and Fig.8. Higher content of fibers induces the lower value of TEC and σ_x too.

INFLUENCE OF UNEQUAL WIDTHS OF WEFT - AND WARP - YARNS

Owing to the conditions of fabrication the dimensions of cross-sections of weft- and warp-yarns are different, which results in the TEC in mentioned directions and also influences the internal stresses, as can be seen in Fig.9 and Fig.10.

INFLUENCE OF THE ELASTICITY MODULUS OF FIBERS

As it is known, the Young's modulus of glass fibers can vary within rather broad limits. If we assume that the other properties of fibers are the same like in previous cases, the changing modulus will induce the variation of TEC and of the thermal stresses of composite material in accordance with Fig.11 and 12.

INFLUENCE OF THE THERMAL RESISTANCE OF MATRIX

Different thermal resistance was expressed by the change of the temperatures T_1^* and T_2^* , that corresponds to the inflection point of the E-T and ν -T curves respectively. The change of T_1^* and T_2^* means only the transition of mentioned curves along the T - axis. The α_M -T dependence is assumed to be unvariable. Fig.13 and 14 show that the increase of thermal resistance of matrix calls the augmentation of TEC and also of thermal stresses.

INFLUENCE OF HIGHER FRACTION OF MATRIX

In all mentioned cases we assumed $H = h$. But in a real laminate-especially prepared by the hand lay-up method - are the adjacent layers of fabric separated by a layer of matrix (in this case $H > h$). The higher content of matrix induces the raising of TEC but reducing of α_1 (as is remarkable in Fig.15 and 16).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To evaluate the accuracy of the theoretical method, the experimental investigations of the thermal responses of a typical glass/polyester laminate subject to temperature changes from 20 to 70°C were carried out. The glass fabric Yplast 35 - Vertex, CSSR - Q = 0.357kg/m², $t_1 = 1.99$ mm, $t_2 = 1.82$ mm, $h = 0.35$ mm $f = 1$ - was used as a reinforcement. Polyester matrix of mark ChS-Polyester 104 was cured at the temperature 20°C in accordance with the recommended procedures. Specimens were prepared by stacking of four layers of the fabric by means of hand lay-up method. The specimens were instrumented with two surface strain-gage rosettes and with a thermocouple. To properly interpret the strain-gage output for determination of thermal dilatation of the material, it was necessary to separate the output due to change in resistivity of the gage with temperature. For this purpose, a steel specimens of known TEC ($10^{-5} K^{-1}$) was instrumented with two pairs of strain-gages, that were acting as dummy gages with connection to the strain gage apparatus Bruel/Kjaer 1531. The circuit diagram is shown in Fig.17.

The true TEC α during temperature change were obtained by adding the known TEC of steel α_s to the apparent TEC α^* , that was determined as a slope of recorded readings

$$\alpha = \alpha^* + \alpha_s$$

Both the specimen and the reference steel sample were subjected to the same temperature environment. The gages were oriented in the weft and warp directions to determine the values α_x and α_y of the composite.

In Fig.18 the experimental and theoretical results are compared. One can see that both values agree very well at the temperature 20°C, where also the values of thermoelastic constants of components response well the reality. The increasing difference is evidently caused by inaccurate accordance of mathematical description with real behaviour of material at higher temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS

The developed computation model can be accepted as convenient for determination of effective TEC of composites with canvas type reinforcement for technical purposes. The model enables also to evaluate the residual stresses that develop within the constituent sub-layers as the material temperature is changing. The cooling from cure temperature down to room one induces in the composite system tensile stresses perpendicular to the fibers. The determined values of these stresses are not negligible in spite of fact that some part of them will diminish due to relaxation processes [1]. The structure of real composites is full of imperfections which increase by means of their concentration effects the danger of residual stresses especially in the case of

CFRP and may significantly influence the fracture process. The findings in the paper are preliminary one since they are based on incomplete and idealized data and on simplified theoretical assumptions. It is very necessary to continue in refining the theoretical method-especially in order to reflect the viscoelastic response of the material - but also in experimental programs to obtain realistic material characteristics, credibility of them would correspond to the accuracy of theoretical procedures.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

x, y, z	-	coordinates
h, H	-	thickness
n	-	number of filaments
t	-	width of yarn
ξ	-	ratio of filaments numbers in the weft and warp direction
Q	-	fabric specific weight
γ	-	density
k	-	volume fraction of fibers
k+	-	weight fraction of fibers
E, G	-	elasticity moduli
ν	-	Poisson's ratio
α	-	thermal expansion coefficient
T	-	temperature
ϵ	-	strain
σ	-	stress

Indices:

1	-	weft yarn
2	-	warp yarn
//	-	direction along fibers
\perp	-	direction perpendicular to fibers
x, y	-	direction of coordinate axis
F	-	fiber
M, β	-	matrix
P	-	polyester
E	-	epoxy

Fig.1 Dimensions of the warp and weft yarns

Fig.2 E - T and ν - T dependence for representative matrixes

Fig.3 Dependence of α_M on temperature

Fig.4 Dependence of TEC of the composite material on temperature

Fig.5 Thermal stresses σ_x , σ_z and σ_y at the x-axis-points for $\Delta T = 50^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fig.6 Thermal stresses at the point (0,0) in dependence on temperature

Fig.7 Dependence of TEC on the thickness of fabric

Fig.8 Thermal stresses at the point (0,0) for $\Delta T = 50^\circ C$

Fig.9 TEC α_x and α_y at temperatures $20^\circ C$ and $70^\circ C$ in dependence of the ratio t_x/t_y

Fig.10 Thermal stresses at the point (0,0) as a function of the ratio t_x/t_y ($\Delta T = 50^\circ\text{C}$)

Fig.11 Influence of the elasticity modulus of fibers on the TEC of composite material

Fig.12 Thermal stresses at the point (0,0) in dependence of the fibers elasticity modulus

Fig.13 Influence of the "thermal resistance" of matrix on TEC

Fig.14 Influence of the "thermal resistance" of matrix on thermal stresses at the point (0,0) for $\Delta T = 120^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fig.15 Dependence of TEC on $\omega = H/h$

Fig.16 Thermal stresses σ_{ii} , σ_z and σ_y at the point $(0,0)$ in dependence of $\omega = H/h$ for the temperature change 20 - 70°C

Fig.17 Circuit diagram for the thermal strains measurement (A - active, D - dummy gauges)

Fig.18 Comparison of the theoretical and experimental results